

Nanoparticle doping – a method of fabrication of highly efficient rare-earth-doped silica fibres for fibre lasers

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Silica optical fibres doped with rare-earths ions are key components of photonics devices like fibre lasers and fibre amplifiers operating in near-infrared spectral region. Since rare earths in silica glass cause clustering and phase separation, the silica glass matrix must be modified, e.g. by alumina. Since starting materials of such components are available only in solid state, conventional chemical vapour deposition methods (like the MCVD method) used for telecom fibre production and based on starting materials in gaseous (or liquid) state had to be modified. This paper deals with ‘nanoparticle-doping’ method by which high-quality thulium-doped and holmium-doped preforms for specialty optical fibre drawing can be prepared. An easy implementation of the nanoparticle-doping method into established technologies belongs to its strong points. High dopant concentration up to 10 mol% of alumina and thousands of ppm of rare earths (and high alumina/rare-earth ratio up to 50/1) distributed homogeneously in preforms (fibres) in macro-, micro- and nano-scale can be achieved by the proposed way. Fibre lasers based on such fibres exhibited low threshold, high slope efficiency (up to 64% in case of thulium-doped fibre lasers and 80% in case of holmium-doped fibre lasers) and high output power (Watts in case of thulium-doped fibre lasers and tens of Watts in case of holmium-doped fibre lasers).

1. Introduction

Silica glass is a unique material optically transparent from ultraviolet to near-infrared spectral region, mechanically, chemically and thermally durable, of high transparency suitable for fabrication of optical fibres.^(1–2) Specialty optical fibres doped with rare earths (RE) can serve as key components of fibre lasers, fibre amplifiers and amplified-spontaneous-emission sources. Unfortunately, only several tens ppm of RE in glass leads to clustering, phase separation and so to unacceptable optical attenuation of the fibres. To avoid these effects, silica glass must be co-doped with other oxides. Starting materials of such modifiers are usually available only in solid state and so established methods of preform and

fibre fabrication must be modified. Latest trends in this field aim at R&D of variety of materials emitting at wide range of wavelengths and at increase of slope efficiency (SLE) together with output power (OP) of fibre lasers based on these RE-doped fibres. Several approaches were proposed.^(3–10) This paper deals with nanoparticle-doping method which lead to production of high-quality active fibres doped with thulium or with holmium capable to achieve high SLE together with high OP of fibre lasers.

2. Experimental

RE-doped fibres were originally fabricated by solution-doping method.^(11–13) This approach makes fabrication of fibre cores doped with $\sim 10^4$ ppm of RE^{3+} and with 5–7 mol% Al_2O_3 possible. In this approach, porous layer of silica particles is deposited into substrate silica tube, impregnated with a solution of RE salts and AlCl_3 , dried, carefully sintered to glassy state and the deposited tube is collapsed to preform. In the case of nanoparticle-doping method^(14,15) a solution of nanoparticles is used instead of solution. When properly performed, interesting preform and fibre properties can be achieved, e.g. doping preform cores with up to $\sim 10^4$ ppm of RE^{3+} and with 7–10 mol% Al_2O_3 homogeneously distributed in the preform (fibre). This ‘nanoparticle’ approach has led to progress of technologies in this field^(16–25) which have made increase of SLE and OP of novel generation of fibre lasers possible.

3. Results and discussion

RE-doped preforms and fibres doped with erbium, ytterbium, thulium and holmium were prepared by the nanoparticle-doping method.^(26–32) Their refractive-index profiles were of smooth shape without central dip, of numerical aperture 0.22–0.26. Composition of preforms determined by electron microprobe analysis corresponded to the determined refractive index; content of Al_2O_3 was of around 7–10 mol%, content of RE^{3+} ions was up to 4000 ppm.

Optical fibres of diameter 125 or 130 μm and of core diameter of around 6 μm were drawn from these

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preforms. Content of RE ions determined at fibres from spectral attenuation measurements corresponded to these values; low background losses of around 20–40 dB/km were achieved. When thulium or holmium-doped fibres prepared by the described way were implemented into fibre laser high SLE together with high OP were achieved.

Example of performance of thulium doped fibre of octagonal geometry (with fluorinated coating) in Fabry–Perrot laser arrangement can be seen at Figure 1.

Example of performance of holmium-doped fibre pumped by thulium-doped fibre laser in tandem arrangement can be seen at Figure 2.

Comparing the achieved values to the state-of-art in the field, good results can be concluded; SLE of 64% together with OP of 5–9 W have recently been achieved with thulium-doped fibre laser.⁽³³⁾ Progress of parameters of holmium-doped fibre lasers can be seen from comparison of recently achieved results: 7 W OP and 74% SLE (2016),⁽³⁴⁾ 8 W OP and 81% SLE (2018),⁽³⁵⁾ 6 W OP and 81% SLE (2020),⁽³⁶⁾ 30 W OP and 86% SLE (2023),⁽³⁷⁾ 1 W OP and 86% SLE (2024),⁽³⁸⁾ 35 W OP and 80% SLE.⁽³⁹⁾

The obtained high OP together with high SLE can be attributed to good homogeneity of prepared preform and fibre cores in macro-, micro- and nano-scope range and to high Al/RE ratio up to 50/1 which can be achieved by the described fabrication process.^(28,38)

4. Conclusions

Described concept of nanoparticle-doping method leads to fabrication of high-quality RE-doped optical fibres for fibre lasers. An easy implementation of this method into established technologies belongs to its strong points. High dopant concentration (high Al/RE up to 50/1) distributed homogeneously in preforms and fibres can be achieved in this way. Fibre lasers based on such fibres exhibited

Figure 1. Performance of thulium-doped fibre laser based on fibre which preform was prepared by the nanoparticle-doping method (64% of SLE, 2.4 W of OP)

Figure 2. Performance of thulium-doped fibre laser based on fibre which preform was prepared by the nanoparticle-doping method (80% of SLE, 25 W of OP)

high SLE, high OP and low threshold. Current research deals with aim of increase of SLE together with OP of thulium fibre lasers and holmium fibre lasers and with study of thermal behaviour of thulium fibre lasers.

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Data availability statement

The data supporting the results of this study are available in Kasik.⁽⁴⁰⁾

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